

Performance Prediction of Capillary Tube for an Air Conditioning System using ANN

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Abstract: The objective of this research paper was to optimize length of a capillary tube in a split type air conditioning system in order to enhance the Coefficient of Performance (COP). The acquired data is used for training and testing the proposed ANN method, which is operated, at different capillary tubes. Using the mathematical data, for training, an ANN model was created based on Feed Forward Neural Network, used for nonlinear mapping between the input and the output parameters. Different activation functions and several rules were used to assess the percentage error between the desired and the predicted values. The optimization was determined by mathematical calculation to evaluate COP of a split-type air conditioning system with a 3 different sizes of capillary tubes. Assumed that, the experimental equipment was designed and constructed to verify the COP data obtained from the calculation. It was observed that the ANN model can predict the COP quite well with statically correlations such as Coefficient of Variance (COV), absolute fraction of variance (R^2), with very low root mean square errors (RMSE). This study shows that, as an alternative to classical modeling techniques, the ANN approach can be used to accurately predict the performance and COP of the Air Conditioning System. The results found that from the theoretical analysis, the COP was changing in a direction contrary to the length of the capillary tube. When the capillary tube length is smaller, COP values tend to be higher.

Keywords— Artificial neural network (ANN), Capillary tube, Vapour Compression Refrigeration, Coefficient of performance (COP), Root Mean Square Errors (RMSE), absolute fraction of variance (R^2) and Coefficient of Variance (COV).

1. INTRODUCTION

The output of refrigeration or air-conditioning systems has been increasing rapidly in recent decades and refrigeration systems become more important for people's daily lives. For example, room air conditioners used in China increased by about 15% per year in the past 10 years, and nowadays the use of air conditioners consumes a lot of electricity, amounting up to 40% of the total electricity consumption in the summer in some cities like Shanghai. Therefore, it is important to make the design process of refrigeration systems

more efficient and the product performance better. Computer simulation is one of the valuable means to accomplish this target.

Air conditioning and refrigeration systems play an important role in industry, infrastructure and households. The industrial sector includes the food industry, textiles, chemicals, printing, transport and others. Infrastructure includes banks, restaurants, schools, hotels and recreational facilities. Therefore, the performance of the equipment is important for the operations associated with those activities.

A simple vapour compression refrigeration system consists of mainly five components namely [6] compressor, condenser, expansion device, evaporator and a filter/drier. The following study is focused towards finding out the effect of the capillary tube on the performance of the refrigeration system. A capillary tube is a small diameter tube which is used for the expansion of the flowing fluid. The pressure difference between the entry and exit ends of the capillary tube is always equal to the pressure difference between the condenser and the evaporator. The diameter of the capillary tube used in the refrigeration appliances varies from 0.5mm to 2.3mm. the effect of the capillary tube has been investigated by many researchers in the past and encouraging results were obtained.

The performance of a simple vapour compression refrigeration system, used in numerous of small refrigeration applications all over the world, deteriorates in actual conditions due to internal and external irreversibility and further due to transient conditions over evaporator and condenser, but there is a simultaneous decrease in theoretical COP of the system, which occurs due to wider gap between condenser and evaporator temperature because of higher value of temperature gradient across evaporator and condenser.

The length of capillary tube mainly decides the evaporator and condenser pressure. Lesser the length higher is the evaporator pressure and vice versa. [4] The length of capillary tube may be theoretically optimized if the heat transfer conditions over evaporator and condenser and so the evaporation and condensation pressures are steady state. But under transient conditions, it will not work for the whole range of temperature in a given cooling job. The accurate size of the capillary tube and its configuration can be predicted with the help of the conventional

method, calculations, for the refrigeration effect, coefficient of performance (COP) of the system and mass flow rate of the system.

Though, conventional method is still used for designing refrigeration systems to determine the required performance, the actual performance obviously deviate from the required one because there is no accurate model used in the design process. So, it is necessary to simulate the model to get actual real time results.

The computer simulation method has been used for designing refrigeration systems and has shown its advantages over the conventional one. With the computer simulation method, the working conditions and the configuration parameters of the system are given at first, then the performance is predicted, and at last the configuration parameters of the system is evaluated based on the performance prediction. If the predicted performance does not meet the requirement, the configuration parameters should be adjusted, and simulation should be done again with the adjusted structural parameters. The process of modifying the parameters and simulating with modified parameters will be iterated until a set of the most suitable parameters is obtained. Such a computation process can be implemented by adding some optimization subprograms or directly operated by users based on their experiences, and can be used for optimum design of refrigeration systems. Stability, Rapidness and Accuracy are the least requirements [1] for a simulation. These three requirements may conflict with each other, and then a compromise has to be made to achieve good results.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The blockage in the capillary tube results in lower injection of refrigerant into the evaporator, so there will be a loss in cooling. Typically, this

problem can be solved by changing a new capillary tube. However, this also results in refrigerant being released from the system, which makes for higher cost and time wastage with low COP. Furthermore, the size of the replacement capillary tube must be the same and some sizes are difficult to source, which makes the problem more complex.

To come over these problems, the objective of this research is to determine the appropriate size of a new capillary tube mathematically that can replace the old blocked one, and by using the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), we can get the results which are very near to the real time operation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The conventional method, which involves the mathematical equations and calculations, gives the COP for different tube lengths, but as discussed it deviates from the actual result due to the many assumptions we have made to construct equation. So there will be many factors which effect when it comes to real time operation, to overcome that, in this paper we are taking the help of ANN to get more accurate results.

Firstly, we are calculating the COP for the different tube lengths with the use of mathematical equations, then these values are fed into the ANN to get the accurate results, the resulting values will give the optimized length of capillary tube. This can be done by comparing the mathematical values with ANN results with respect to the capillary tube length.

The specifications used in the ANN are as follows:

Network type: Feed – forward backpropagation

Training function: TRAINBR

Adaption learning function: LEARNGDM

Transfer function: TANSIG

With 2 layers and 10 neurons.

Fig. 1 Representation of AN Network

4. AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEM

Air conditioning is the process of altering the properties of air to more comfortable conditions, typically with the aim of distributing the conditioned air to an occupied space such as a building or a vehicle to improve thermal comfort and indoor air quality. In common use, an air conditioner is a device that removes heat from the air inside a building or vehicle, thus lowering the air temperature. The cooling is typically achieved through a *refrigeration cycle*, but sometimes evaporation or free cooling is used. The air conditioning system is basically the refrigeration system.

4.1 WORKING PRINCIPLE

A domestic refrigeration system is in complete compliance with the Clausius statement of the second law of thermodynamics. The Clausius statement simply states that a refrigeration system cannot operate unless its compressor is driven by an external power source, such as an electric motor [3]. In this case, the compressor leaves a trace in the surroundings by consuming some energy in the form of work by the electric motor so that to transfer heat from the colder body to a warmer one.

Fig. 2 P – V diagram of a refrigeration system

Courtesy @google images

Fig. 3 P – h diagram of a refrigeration system

Courtesy @google images

- *Process 1 – 2*: Isentropic compression in compressor.
- *Process 2 – 3*: Constant pressure heat rejection in condenser.
- *Process 3 – 4*: Isenthalpic expansion in expansion device.
- *Process 4 – 1*: Constant pressure heat absorption in evaporator.

4.2 IMPORTANCE OF CAPILLARY TUBE

A capillary tube is a common expansion device used in small sized refrigeration and air conditioning systems. A capillary tube is a constant area expansion device used in a vapor compression refrigeration system located between the condenser and evaporator and

whose function is to reduce the high pressure in the condenser to low pressure in the evaporator. Capillary tubes are extensively used where load is fairly constant due to its advantage such as cheap, reliable, simple to install, zero maintenance and requirement of a low starting torque to run the compressor.

The term capillary tube means “hair-like”. It is so called because of its very small bore diameter. The inside diameter of the capillary tube used for the purpose of refrigeration ranges from about 0.5 mm to 2.30 mm. longer the capillary tube and/or smaller the inside diameter of the capillary tube, greater is the pressure drop it can create in the refrigerant flow. In other words, greater will be the pressure difference needed between the high pressure side and the low pressure side to establish a given flow rate of the refrigerant. Though, the use of different materials is adapted, for the capillary tube, in the practice. Usually they are made of copper to give maximum performance.

Researchers are focused towards finding out the influence of the geometrical configurations of a capillary tube on the performance of the refrigeration system. The accurate size of the capillary tube and its configuration can be predicted with the help of the calculations for the refrigeration effect, coefficient of performance (cop) of the system and mass flow rate of the system. The capillary tube can be straight, helical coiled and also serpentine coiled and all three configurations have their own distinct effect on the system performance.

By now, from above discussion, you should have acquainted with capillary tube and how they affect COP. Our research predicts the optimized length of capillary tube to give best performance.

4.3 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK (ANN)

Artificial neural network is a computational paradigm that differs substantially from those based on the standard Von-Neumann architecture. ANN generally learn from experience rather than explicit program. ANN is inspired from structure of biological neural network and their way of solving problems. The philosophy of the ANN approach is some key ingredients from biology and out of those construct simple mathematical models that exhibit most of the above mentioned features.

Artificial neural networks are one of the most powerful computer modelling techniques based on statistical approach, currently being used in many fields of engineering for modelling complex relationships, which are difficult to describe with physical models. There has been continual increase in research interest in the applications of ANNs in the refrigeration system modelling [1]. Numerous applications of neural network related to refrigeration system are developed.

Neural networks consist of arrays of simple active units linked by weighted connections. ANN consists of multiple layers of neurons arranged in such a way that each neuron in one layer is connected with each neuron in the next layer. The network we used in our study in multilayer feed forward neural network with learning scheme of the back propagation of errors. Neurons are the fundamental processing element of an ANN, which are arranged in layers that make up the global architecture.

After a neural network has been created, it needs to be configured and then trained. Configuration involves arranging the network so that it is compatible with the problem you want to solve, as defined by sample data. After the network has been configured, the adjustable network parameters (called weights and biases)

need to be tuned, so that the network performance is optimized. This tuning process is referred to as training the network. Configuration and training require that the network be provided with example data.

The set of measured values of the refrigeration parameters were used as target data for back propagation neural network training. Each training data set consisted of three input nodes and one output nodes. The performance of the neural network depends on the number of hidden layers and the number of nodes in the hidden layer. The structure of the network applied for predicting the performance was chosen by trial and error method. Training was done based on the back propagation algorithm coding. The architecture of the proposed four-layer network is given in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Architecture of ANN

5. MATHEMATICAL EQUATIONS

The system is assumed to work as an isentropic process and there are three different sizes of capillary tubes in this calculation.

Mass flow rate (m):

$$m = C_1 + C_2 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} + C_3 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 + C_4 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_5 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_6 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_7 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} +$$

$$C_8 \cdot T_{evap} \cdot T_{cond}^2 + C_9 \cdot T_{evap}^2 \cdot T_{cond}^2 \tag{1}$$

Where,

Flow rate(m) = mass flow rate (kg/h)

C_i =Constant, $i= 1,2,3...9$

T_{evap} =Temperature at evaporator(°C)

T_{cond} = Temperature at condenser (°C)

Substituting the mass flow rate data in the above equation we have:

From equation (1), we get the value of constants as:

$$C_1 = 117.7158$$

$$C_2 = 2.7149$$

$$C_3 = -0.2007$$

$$C_4 = -0.8751$$

$$C_5 = 8.5 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$C_6 = 0$$

$$C_7 = 0.0197$$

$$C_8 = 3.3866 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$C_9 = 3.1417 \times 10^{-4}$$

From the above constants, we can rewrite the equation (1) as:

$$m = 117.7158 + 2.7149 \cdot T_{evap} - 0.2007 \cdot T_{evap}^2 - 0.8751 \cdot T_{cond} + 8.5 \times 10^{-3} \cdot T_{cond}^2 + 0.0197 \cdot T_{evap}^2 \cdot T_{cond} + 3.3866 \times 10^{-4} \cdot T_{evap} \cdot T_{cond}^2 + 3.1417 \times 10^{-4} \cdot T_{evap}^2 \cdot T_{cond}^2$$

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mathematical results for different inputs are presented in table 1.

Tc	Te	Capillary tube in inches	COP(math)
40	0	3	6.199
		4	6.266
		5	6.322
	5	3	7.221
		4	7.095

	10	5	6.78
		3	8.97
		4	8.821
45	0	5	8.639
		3	5.244
		4	5.305
	5	5	5.357
		3	6.005
		4	5.894
	10	5	5.758
		3	6.536
		4	6.421
50	5	5	6.28
		3	4.473
		4	4.531
	10	5	4.579
		3	5.08
		4	4.98
	55	5	4.858
		3	6.134
		4	6.019
60	10	5	5.878
		3	3.843
		4	3.898
	5	5	3.944
		3	3.358
		4	3.287
	0	5	3.201
		3	4.08
		4	3.999
60	5	5	3.897
		3	3.56
		4	3.618
60	0	5	3.666
		3	3.264
		4	3.191
60	5	5	3.101
		3	3.969
		4	

10	4	3.882
	5	3.776

TABLE 1
MATHEMATICAL RESULTS

Now, these values are fed into the ANN to get accurate results, which are, show in the table 2.

T_c	T_e	Capillary tube in inches	COP (ANN)
40	0	3	6.1982
		4	6.2662
		5	6.3237
	5	3	7.2242
		4	7.092
		5	6.6019
	10	3	8.8961
		4	8.8355
		5	8.6394
45	0	3	5.2432
		4	5.2493
		5	5.3538
	5	3	6.0062
		4	5.8954
		5	5.7584
	10	3	6.5382
		4	6.4199
		5	6.2819
	0	3	4.4765
		4	4.5306
		5	4.5822
		3	5.0759

The above results are now compared with mathematical values and results are presented in the following graphs:

50	5	4	4.9809
		5	4.8574
	10	3	5.0279
		4	5.6152
55	0	5	5.8739
		3	3.8401
		4	3.8936
	5	5	3.9475
		3	3.3712
		4	3.2842
60	10	5	3.1953
		3	3.9114
	0	4	4.0003
		5	3.9029
60	0	3	3.5583
		4	3.6248
		5	3.659
	5	3	3.1955
		4	3.1673
		5	3.1353
	10	3	3.7844
		4	3.8818
		5	3.7741

TABLE 2
ANN RESULTS

T_c – Condenser temperature (° C)

T_e – Evaporator temperature (° C)

Results are taken into account by considering RMSE, R², COV.

Fig. 4 Mathematical vs ANN Results

Fig. 5 Tube lengths vs Mathematical, ANN Results

Mathematical models are typically used to model a system when the system is not so complicated, but when the complexity of a system is increased other methods should be used for modelling. ANN is typically used when the behaviour of system is the most complicated or the linguistic rules are needed to define the behaviour of a system. But in a condition between above-mentioned ANN is a good

modelling method which can produce good results. The main advantages of using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) include, it can handle large amount of data sets, it has the ability to implicitly detect complex nonlinear relationships between dependent and independent variables, it has ability to detect all possible interactions between predictor variables, etc.

Fig. 6 Regression plots from Neural Network

Neural networks often exhibit patterns similar to those exhibited by humans. However, this is more of interest in cognitive sciences than for practical examples. Neural networks are quite simple to implement. These factors driven us to use the ANN, and after the number of epochs it started to give the values which are very close to

the expected result with very minimal errors. Thus, ANN is very best approach to solve large data sets for optimal results.

From regression analysis graph it is clear that there is very minimal error, where the obtained results are the best fit to the system.

Fig. 7 represents the best capillary tube length with corresponds to COP obtained from both Mathematical equations and ANN.

Fig. 7 Comparison of tube length w.r.t COP's

The pressure difference across the capillary tube is the driving force for the refrigerant to flow through it, hence mass flow rate through the capillary tube increases with increase in pressure difference across it. Thus the mass flow rate through the capillary tube increases as the condenser pressure increases and/or the evaporator pressure decreases. With constantly falling temperature over evaporator, refilling of it with more and more liquid refrigerant causes increase in heat transfer coefficient which maintains the refrigeration rate at falling temperature.

In Our study we acknowledge that larger capillary tubes decrease the tendency of refilling but offers less evaporator temperature while shorter capillary tubes ensure higher cop initially but it deteriorates at a faster rate in lower temperature range.

This study reveals that, by use of Neural Network, for vapor compression refrigeration system, models can be developed to predict the COP through ANN method. The best model is selected based on the best performance error for different network configurations. In addition, the models have been evaluated by means of the percentage deviation between the predicted values and the actual values.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper mainly focuses on enhancing the performance of a refrigeration cycle (Air Conditioning System), to do so there are so many methods/ways, one of the effective way (in terms of cost with less ambiguity) is to alter the capillary tube length with suitable dimension which meets our criteria (high COP). The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach has been applied to vapor compression refrigeration

system as an alternative to the classical approaches, which are usually complicated, require an enormous amount of the experimental data, and may yield inaccurate results. In order to gather the data for training and testing the proposed ANN method, Mathematical values have been tested for its performance at different capillary tube length with constant diameter. Using the three different parameters, namely, *condenser temperature*, *evaporator temperature* and *capillary length* which are the input parameters with target value as COP. The ANN model based on the back propagation algorithm was created, the performance of ANN predictions was measured considering the three criteria's, Root mean square error (RMSE), Correlation coefficient (R^2), and Coefficient of variance (COV).

We used ANN to find %error between the theoretical model and simulated model, as ANN gives accurate results, our study found that %error was about **4.9%** and the optimized results are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Capillary tube length} &= 3 \text{ inches} \\ \text{COP at that length} &= 8.97 \end{aligned}$$

So, it can be concluded that a capillary tube with a length of **3 inches**, among three, gives the maximum COP of **8.97**.

8. FUTURE WORK

The above results are used in our further work, where we will discuss about how the COP of a system can be effected by changing the specifications of the capillary tube. This paper focused on ANN method to simulate the model, where the same can be done using CFD which we will be doing further.

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